

INDIVIDUAL PROTECTION AGAINST CRIME THROUGH PREVENTION

Axrorov Damir Aslam o'g'li

Student of Tashkent State University of Law

Akhrorov0303gmail.com

+998906003153

Annotation: Human rights must be safeguarded and defended by the state. Prevention of crimes is not an afterthought when it comes to maintaining state protection and human rights protection. In this respect, one of the primary responsibilities of the state, represented by authorized entities, is to build the legal and organizational foundations of the crime prevention system, as well as its general operating norms, fundamental principles, and guiding principles. A legislative study reveals that the legal framework that protects human rights, society, and the state from unlawful intrusions falls behind the requirements of reality and law enforcement practice.

Key words: Human rights, guarantees of citizens' rights, state, principle of humanism, preventive protection, law.

Introduction. Individual protection against crime is centered on the interests of society and the state and is integrated into the sociology and legal system. This philosophy derives from the fact that this protection is based on conformity with governmental and social obligations, which guarantee the protection and safety of the individual. Simultaneously, society and the state transfer their rights and advantages to a person who is safeguarded on their behalf, displaying not their own priority but that of the individual, person, and citizen. In such a scenario, the state and society gain, demonstrate humanism, democracy, and a measure of nobility. Without ensuring adequate prevention of crimes by those who are capable of committing them, society and the state will be unable of protecting the individual against criminal intrusions. Realizing the concept of humanism, preventative

protection, which focuses on protecting the safety of society's members, is not aimed at those who have already committed crimes (the state punishes them), but rather at those who can still be prevented from pursuing a criminal path. By preventing crimes, assistance is supplied to those who would commit them, while those against whom they could be perpetrated are protected. Constantly, crime precedes punishment, and warning always before crime.

In fact, a shrewd lawmaker would prefer to avoid a crime than be forced to penalize for it. Identifying the perpetrator, solving the crime, and ensuring the imminence of punishment are very essential, but preventing crime and protecting a person from criminal intrusion is paramount¹. Preventative protection plays an important role here. It employs all social mechanisms and the power of the state to erect dependable barriers against crime. Simultaneously, preventive protection functions as a unique kind of social and legal regulation, whereas maintaining the security of the individual manifests as a response of the state and society to crimes. Protection of the individual against criminal intrusions encompasses all criminologically significant social factors. It is incorporated into the system of criminology, and consequently sociology and law. This philosophy stems from the fact that the protection of the individual is predicated on conformity with societal norms and the articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which guarantee the rights and freedoms of citizens, safeguard human life and health, property, etc. Individuals are safeguarded by law and society. Focusing specifically on the prevention of crimes, preventative protection highlights the individual who can perform a criminally punishable act and the individual who can become its victim.

¹ Рябков Николай Сергеевич (2015). Защита интересов личности, общества и государства от преступных посягательств и иных угроз: проблемы правоприменения. Эпоха науки 229 с.

Concurrently, this protection serves as a link between population-wide and individual preventative efforts². This circumstance has elements of the consistent growth of social prevention, which includes legal tools. The system for defending the individual from criminal intrusions, in which constitutional protection plays a vital role, consists of the following components. The initial is an individual's social security. All social entities whose rights and responsibilities pertain to preserving the safety of individuals against criminal intrusions should be involved here. Individual economic security is the second component. This relates to financial and economic matters, as well as the infringement of citizens' relevant rights by criminal acts. The protection of individuals against the influence of the shadow economy is distinctive in this context. Legal protection of the individual, which includes prosecutorial oversight, court protection, etc., is the third factor. This refers to the legal protection of a person against criminal acts and the establishment of conditions for the safety of individuals. This may include rule-making, information and legal support for activities to ensure this security, building a legal foundation for protecting a person's rights and freedoms, legal control, creating more advanced legal mechanisms for protecting citizens from crime, generalizing and disseminating best practices, etc. Notable are the prosecutor's office and courts, the Ministry of the Interior and the State Security Service, the justice authorities, the tax inspectorate and customs service, notary services, etc. This is significantly influenced by advocacy. As already noted, crime prevention cannot be separated from protecting public safety and bolstering the rule of law. Although unclear concepts "appear" here, their coherence is clear. Protection of the individual and society from crime can be defined as a system of social relations determined by the needs of the development of a democratic state, the formation and improvement of which contributes to the tranquility of citizens, the consistency and rhythm of people's

² Михайлов Валентин Иванович (2015). Защита интересов личности, общества и государства от преступных посягательств и иных угроз: проблемы правоприменения. Журнал российского права, (2 (218)), 94 с.

lives, the provision of personal and property inviolability, honor in mutual communication, and dignity, as well as favorable conditions for the exercise by each person of his rights and freedoms. The objective of preventative protection, which is directly related to ensuring public safety and upholding the rule of law, is a person's life and health, mental tranquility, rights and liberties, and property³. Moreover, there is a close connection between crime prevention and law enforcement. This refers to comprehensive prevention: social and moral, legal, general, and private warning, which relates to the field of criminal law prevention, general and individual prevention of both criminal and victim behavior, and by branches of knowledge – administrative-legal, criminal procedure, forensic, penitentiary, operational-search, etc. Therefore, preventive protection safeguards all social and personal-human values from criminal intrusions. Regarding this, it is possible to discuss the protective role of preventative protection, which is directly related to the protection of citizens from rule of law infractions.

Conclusion. In general, we are discussing the protection of citizens. Protecting a person from hooliganism requires a variety of social, legal, economic, and other means⁴, as does the matter of maintaining public order. As demonstrated by actual events, sophisticated preventative measures included into the system of maintaining public order contribute to the effective implementation of hooliganism protection. All of these actions are linked, giving public protection of order against egregious transgressions, which are connected with a manifest disregard for society, and protection of the individual from the violence utilized in hooliganism. There is also a connection with the rule of law, which unifies social (legal) connections based on the simplest conduct rules: obey the law⁵. Such rules are based on social morality

³Михайлов Валентин Иванович (2015). Защита интересов личности, общества и государства от преступных посягательств и иных угроз: проблемы правоприменения. Журнал российского права, (2 (218)), 95 с.

⁴Каракетова , Д. . (2021). Безориликни олдини олишнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари. Jamiyat Va Innovatsiyalar, 2(7/S), 105 с.

⁵ Eshkobilov, S. (2022). Criminological description of organized crime. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 4(04), 3-4 p.

norms, in which the state, society, and citizens have an interest, and without which social life is inconceivable. These norms establish the fundamental conditions of human communication, which safeguard the individual and society against criminal incursions by preventing crimes. According to and in compliance with such regulations, preventive protection of a person must be carried out. To enhance the efficacy of such protection, however, both the prevention of criminal and victim behavior is required. These are the primary activities designed to ensure public safety and human protection. All components of the "preventive complex" must function normally to ensure the protection of public order and the protection of the person. This is a kind of preventive system.

References:

1. Eshkobilov, S. (2022). Criminological description of organized crime. *The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology*, 4(04), 1-6.
2. Nodirbek Jalilov. (2022). INTRODUCTION AND LEGAL BASIS OF THE INSTITUTION OF INDIVIDUAL PREVENTION OF CRIMES. *The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology*, 4(06), 48–52. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajpslc/Volume04Issue06-08>
3. Абдурасулова, К. Р., Салаев, Н. С., & Каракетова, Д. Ю. (2014). Иктисодиёт соҳасидаги жиноятларни декриминализация қилиш муаммолари. Монография. Тошкент давлат юридик университети Илмий-услубий кенгаширининг 2014 йгт 25 сентябрдаги 1-сонли баённомасига асосан нашрга тавсия этилган. Т.: Noshir,-2014.-Б, 14.
4. Михайлов Валентин Иванович (2015). Защита интересов личности, общества и государства от преступных посягательств и иных угроз: проблемы правоприменения. *Журнал российского права*, (2 (218)), 91-101.
5. Рябков Николай Сергеевич (2015). Защита интересов личности, общества и государства от преступных посягательств и иных угроз: проблемы правоприменения. *Эпоха науки*, (4), 228-232.

6. Каракетова , Д. . (2021). Безориликни олдини олишнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари. Jamiyat Va Innovatsiyalar, 2(7/S), 102–112.
<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp102-112>
7. Jalilov, N. (2022). PROFILAKTIK HISOB TUSHUNCHASI VA UNI HUQUQIY TARTIBGA SOLISH MUAMMOLARI. Academic research in modern science, 1(9), 313-318.